

Two Velocities in Bound State Quantum Mechanics?

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In a number of previous notes, two velocities in bound state quantum mechanics have been discussed. The first is classical velocity, linked to the wavefunction $W(x)$ by $(-1/2m)[d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x)$ and the second, related to an average conditional momentum $u(x)/m = 1/m [d/dx W(x)] / W(x)$. Although we have discussed these two velocities before, we try to bring together various pieces of information and try to clarify some ideas here.

Exp(ipx)

The wavefunction for a free quantum particle, such as an electron, is given by $\exp(ipx)$ with $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = \sin^2(px) + \cos^2(px)$, suggesting an interplay or resonance between two linked, but independently averaging probability channels. The free electron particle wavefunction may be a little misleading as $d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx)$, $d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) = (ip)(-ip) \exp(ipx)$ etc. In other words, ignoring signs and "i", p^*p (the square of the first derivative) equals the second derivative. This seems to suggest an almost classical nature with momentum p and kinetic energy $p^*p/2m$. In fact, one would immediately assume $1/2m p^*p$ is the kinetic energy of this quantum particle and expect Newtonian mechanics to apply in the sense that if $\exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction in a large region with no potential, $\exp(ip_1 x)$ might be the free particle wavefunction in another large region with a constant potential V_1 with $p_1^*p_1/2m + V_1 = p^*p/2m + 0$. We argue it is important to realize the free quantum particle $\exp(ipx)$ is already being linked to classical mechanics, in particular conservation of energy.

The question arises what to do if the quantum particle is placed in a region with a potential $V(x)$ everywhere. It seems the potential should scatter the particle, but that one does not know the particle's precise location if it is undergoing some kind of zitterbewegung motion. Thus, one might suggest a conditional probability based on:

$$P(p/x) = [f_p \exp(ipx)] / W(x) \text{ where } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

One may use this definition to create various conditional averages of p to even and odd powers. If $f(p) = f(-p)$, odd powers of p will pick up $i \sin(kx)$ while even, $\cos(px)$. To make everything real one could add an $-i$ factor to odd powers of p . The spatial derivative does this automatically. For example:

$$[d/dx W(x)]/W(x) = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } ip f_p \exp(ipx)] = \langle ip \text{ conditional} \rangle = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } 2 p \sin(px) f_p \quad ((2))$$

As argued in a previous note $W(x)$ is a normalization function, called the wavefunction in quantum mechanics. $W(x)$ mimics $\exp(ipx)$ in the sense that a small change in x leads to:

$$d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx) \quad \text{and for } W(x) \quad d/dx W(x) = \langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle W(x).$$

In previous notes, we called $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$, $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ as it is real.

Thus, $W(x)$ tries to move through space in a similar manner to $\exp(ipx)$, but with p replaced with the conditional average $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$. One may also create the conditional average of p^*p ($1/2m$) namely, $1/2m [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^*p \text{ fp } \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$. As argued earlier, this should be linked to $.5m v(x)v(x)$, the classical kinetic energy at x , because it is assumed that the $p^*p/2m$ for a free electron obeys classical mechanics. Thus, one may obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$1/2m [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^*p \text{ fp } \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = -1/2m [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) \quad ((3))$$

The problem is that $u(x)/m$ does not equal $v(x)$, the classical velocity, so there are two velocities in bound state quantum mechanics. (Actually $u(x)$ and $v(x)$ become equal for part of a bound wavefunction outside of a potential region, i.e. $W(x)$ proportional to $\exp(-ax)$ where a is a constant, but we consider regions with a potential in this note.)

The second velocity, $u(x)/m$, appears in many places because the conditional probability ((1)) contains $1/W(x)$ in the denominator. Taking d/dx of a conditional average quantity leads to a term with $-1/[W(x)W(x)] d/dx W(x)$, in other words, $u(x)$ appears. In addition, $d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = 2 [W(x)W(x)] u(x)$ which may also be written as $d/dx s(x) = 2 s(x) u(x) - 2 W(x)W(x) u(x)$ with $s(x)$ is Shannon's spatial entropy $-[WW] \ln[WW]$. Thus, $u(x)$ seems to be important in quantum mechanics, especially since it is related to changes in quantities as one changes from one x to another.

It may be shown that:

$$.5m \text{ Integral } dx \quad W(x)W(x) u(x)/mu(x)/m = .5m \text{ Integral } dx \quad v(x)v(x) \quad ((4))$$

But $.5mv(x)v(x)$ changes according to Newton's laws, while $.5m u(x)/m u(x)/m$ does not (except in one case). To see this, consider:

$$.5m du/dx = -.5m u(x)u(x) - .5m v(x)v(x) \quad ((5))$$

Taking d/dx of both sides yields:

$$.5m d/dx d/dx u = -m u(x) d/dx u(x) - m v(x) d/dx v(x) \quad ((6))$$

But $m v(x)d/dx v(x) = \text{Force}(x)$ so:

$$-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} + \text{Force}(x) = -m u(x) \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} \quad ((7))$$

Thus, in general $-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} / m \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2}$ does not respond as a velocity governed by Newton's laws, unless $-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} / m \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} = 0$. For this case $\frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} = b$ and $u(x) = bx$, where b is a constant.

In such a case, $-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} / m \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2}$ behaves as if governed by Newton's laws. Furthermore, ((5)) with $du/dx = b$ shows there is a kind of resonance between $-\frac{1}{2}m v(x)v(x)$ and $-\frac{1}{2}m u(x)u(x)$ with the latter behaving like a potential energy. If one considers $\text{Force}(x) = -m u(x) b$ for this case, then one has a force proportional to $u(x)$ and a potential energy proportional to $u(x)u(x)$. This fits the quantum oscillator. It turns out that in addition, there is a link to classical statistical mechanics because of this behaviour in $d/dx [u(x)u(x)]$.

It may be shown for quantum mechanics that $W(x)W(x) = \text{density}(x)$ and that:

$$d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x)W(x) u(x) \quad ((8))$$

One might argue that the form of ((8)) could be applied to many systems, but it should be noted that here, $u(x)$ is linked to $v(x)$ by ((5)) and also by the following equation, obtained by taking d/dx of ((3)):

$$(-1/2m) u(x) = 1 / [v(x)v(x)] [\text{Force}(x) + 1/2m \{ [d/dx]^3 W(x) \} / W(x)] \quad ((9))$$

For the case of the quantum oscillator, we have seen that $u(x)$ is proportional to x or the $\text{Force} = -kx$. In such a case ((8)) seems to have a relationship with classical statistical mechanics.

Consider a dilute classical gas, at temperature T in a region with a potential $V(x)$. In such a case, the particles may have all potential (no translational kinetic energy) at one end of the box, in addition to thermal energy. Each particle will gain translational kinetic energy as potential energy is lost. In such a problem, statistical mechanics gives $\text{density}(x) = C \exp(-V(x)/T)$. If one moves from one x to another an infinitesimal distance away then:

$$d/dx \text{density} = \text{density}(x) (1/T) [-d/dx V(x)] = \text{density}(x) 1/T \text{Force}(x) \quad ((10))$$

For the case of the quantum oscillator ground state ((5)), $\text{density}(x)$ matches the classical statistical result with $T = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{k/m} = E$ ground state because $u(x)$ is proportional to the force.

Thus, having $u(x)$ proportional to $\text{Force}(x)$ gives a direct link between quantum and classical statistical mechanics for the ground state oscillator. It should be noted, however, that $u(x)$ is proportional to $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$. For the classical mechanical oscillator $\langle p \rangle = 0$ as there is a particle with p moving to the right for every one with p moving to the left, so there is no non zero $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$. Quantum mechanics is still different even in this case for which the two spatial densities are the same. It should be noted that even though $u(x) d/dx u(x)$ is

proportional to $v(x)$ $d/dx v(x)$, $u(x)$ and $v(x)$ are very different as $d/dx u(x)=b$ a constant. Such is not the case for $v(x)$. $u(x)u(x)$ is proportional to the potential energy which is also proportional to $\ln(W(x)W(x))$ in this case. Thus, for this case:

$$u(x)u(x) C = \ln[W(x)W(x)] = .25 [d/dx W(x)W(x)]^2 C \quad ((11))$$

In other words, Shannon's spatial entropy is proportional to potential energy density $V(x) W(x)W(x)$.

Another way to consider classical statistical mechanical density is:

$$\text{density}(x) = C \exp(1/T (-E + .5m v(x)v(x))) \quad ((12))$$

Then $d/dx \text{density}(x)$ is proportional to $\text{density}(x) d/dx [.5m v(x)v(x)]$.

This is closer to the quantum mechanical picture for the ground state oscillator. In such a case, $d/dx [.5m v(x)v(x)]$ is proportional to $d/dx \{ .5m u(x)u(x) \}$ which in turn is proportional to $u(x)$. Thus, one is obtaining a link with classical statistical mechanics, because $[u(x)u(x)]$ is behaving in a conservative manner with its d/dx proportional to the force x .

Correspondence Principle

If one considers a quantum mechanical system with a high energy eigenvalue, $v(x)$ and $u(x)$ are still present. There may be very periodic narrow peaks in the density $W(x)W(x)$ function. The envelope of the density function, however, may approach $C/v(x)$, the classical density function according to the correspondence principle. If one considers ((4)) applied to a narrow (almost infinitesimal) peak with density zeros at each end, then one does not have to integrate and:

$$1/v v^*v = u^*u \quad \text{or} \quad u = \sqrt{v} \quad ((12))$$

This gives a different link between u and v for high energies. ((8)) still applies. Consider moving from a peak with classical density $1/v(x_1)$ to the next peak with $1/v(x_2)$. The distance between x_1 and x_2 is very small. Consider replacing the descending slope with a straight falling line, and the ascending portion (to x_2) with a straight rising line. Then, one may apply ((8)) to each line.

For the first $d \text{density}(x) / dx = \text{slope} = -1/v(x_1) \sqrt{v(x_1)}$ and for the second $d/dx \text{density} = \text{slope} = 1/v(x_2) \sqrt{v(x_2)}$

The change in density is then:

-Area of first triangle + Area of second

The area of each triangle is $.5 \text{ base height}$. The heights are $1/v(x_1)$ and $1/v(x_2)$.
 Slope=height/base, so base=height/slope. Then:

$d/dx .5 v(x)^{-3/2}$ should approximate the density difference using $u(x)$ or:

Density difference approximation = $.75 v(x)^{-5/2} d/dx v(x)$

Classically one has:

$d/dx 1/v(x) = -v(x)^{-2} d/dx v(x)$ which is similar given the crude approximation used.

The point seems to be that for large energy eigenvalues, even though one still has quantum mechanical “humps”, a link between $u(x)/m$ and $v(x)$ (i.e. $u(x)/m = \text{sqrt}(v(x))$) allows for an envelope (touching peak values) to behave in a classical way in terms of density. It is $u(x)$, however, that governs quantum mechanical density changes $d/dx \text{ density}(x) = 2 \text{ density}(x) u(x)$, so $u(x)$ as $\text{sqrt}(v(x))$ allows for this classical behaviour if one only examines peaks.

Conclusion

In conclusion, bound state quantum mechanics seems to be based on two velocities. The first is $v(x)$, the classical velocity, which links the conditional average of $p^2/2m$ to Newtonian mechanics. The second $u(x)/m$ does not seem to be linked to Newton’s laws (at least in terms of $V(x)$ only). It seems that $u(x)/m$ comes into the picture because of conditional averaging which use $1/W(x)$ as part of the probability (i.e. $\int p \exp(ipx)/W(x)$), where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. $W(x)$ mimics the behaviour of the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ as one moves from one x point to another, except that it replaces p with $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ i.e. an average momentum. This quantum type motion differs from $v(x)$ the classical one even though $\int dx .5 W(x)W(x) u(x)u(x) = .5 \int dx W(x)W(x) v(x)v(x)$. In one case $d/dx [u(x)u(x)]$ is proportional to $d/dx [v(x)v(x)]$, although $u(x)$ is still not equal to $v(x)$. This is the case of the ground state oscillator and for such a case, the quantum mechanical density is of the same form of the classical statistical mechanical one, although there is still no $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ for the statistical mechanical case. Thus, it is $u(x)/m$ which allows for quantum mechanics to approach statistical mechanical forms for the ground state oscillator because it $d/dx [u(x)u(x)]$ reacts in a conservative way to the influence of the force $F(x)$. In the ground state oscillator case, this is because $u(x)u(x)$ becomes proportional to $V(x)$, the potential. Thus, it may be the dynamical behaviour of $u(x)/m$ which has a large effect on quantum mechanics. One may note that $d/dx \text{ density}(x) = 2 \text{ density}(x) u(x)$, so $u(x)$ also governs how the spatial density changes in addition to other quantities such as Shannon’s spatial entropy density. It should also be noted that because $W(x)$ mimics $\exp(ipx)$, there may be much periodicity in a bound quantum state.